

EARTH SCIENCES

LITHO-FACIAL ANALYSIS USING BOREHOLE METHODS IN DETERMINING SEDIMENTARY CONDITIONS

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Abstract

90% of extracted oil-gas condensate is made up of productive layer sediments. A more detailed study of these sediments is of great theoretical and important practical importance. For this reason, studying its characteristics, determining the composition, conditions of formation, and origin of the collected sediments is one of the main issues. All natural events (catastrophes) have a unique effect on the sediment accumulation process. Through facies analysis, it is possible to recreate the depositional conditions. At the same time, facies analysis allows determining the development process of rocks with different lithological composition, especially rock-collectors, as well as places rich in minerals.

Keywords: geophysical methods, litofacies, sedimentary, facies analysis, well logging.

Purpose of the work

Facies analysis is understood as a set of studies that serve to study the conditions of sedimentation. The subject of facies analysis is the facies understood as a depositional environment, young or old, manifested in sediment or rock. A complex of genetic traits is used to restore the deposition conditions. Facies are divided into 3 broad and large-scale groups: continental, transitional and marine facies group. These large facies groups, in turn, are divided into different macrofacies (alluvial) and facies (colluvial and delluvial). Facies, in turn, can be divided into microfacies (proluvial).

Core materials are the main source of geological information about the deep layers of the Earth's crust. However, in practice, the core is taken not from the entire well wall, but only from the intervals where the productive layers can be opened, depending on the interval, the core removal is rarely 100%, and the diameter is not larger than 2.5-5 cm. At the same time, soft, semi-soft and strongly cracked rocks are generally not preserved in the core.

Finally, it is not always possible to raise it from the necessary interval, when they are taken and brought to the surface of the earth, the properties of the rocks and the fluids absorbed in them change clearly, so the results of the analysis of core and mud do not give adequate ideas about the geological section.

At the same time, the mining-geophysical studies carried out in practically all wells are used to determine the individual layers and their properties with sufficient accuracy, to study their distribution, change in thickness, washings, inconsistencies, etc. allows to determine.

In modern times, geological models based on geological-geophysical data are of great importance in forecasting the reserves of the field. Paleosedimentation, changes in facies conditions, and investigation of

the period of sediment accumulation are involved in the construction of more accurate geological models. The lithological composition, structure and conditions of formation of rocks are interrelated and characterized by qualitative and quantitative characteristics. The physical properties of rocks can be measured directly by rock samples or distance borehole methods. As a result, the parameters of the physical fields contain a lot of geological information, including the depositional conditions of the rocks. Also, complex borehole methods are closely related to genetic types of facies, development of post-sedimentary processes, selection of productive reservoirs in cross section. The main purpose of well logging is to obtain a geological description of the section, to study the structure of the field, to conduct regional studies, to calculate reserves and to help geologists to control the development of the field.

In 1984, V.S. Muromcev investigated the forecasting of lithological oil-gas traps in terrigenous reservoirs by applying borehole methods. The scientific work in which the facies models of sandy deposits are comprehensively analyzed has been published. Also, a local prediction method of oil and gas lithological traps based on facies analysis of terrigenous rocks using SP, GR curves is also proposed here.

Considering the variety of facies conditions and the limitations of generalized forms of SP (GR) curves, it is possible to interpret them in a certain sequence. Initially, the facies group of the studied sediments (continental, transitional, marine) is determined. Then, the condition of the sediment flows is determined according to the forms of the SP (GR) of the considered group, and the analysis is carried out on the basis of logging. Based on the analysis of the wells, a spatial distribution model of facies conditions is selected. When choosing this model, the comparison of the facies in the collection conditions with the core material should be taken

into account. As a result, this analysis allows not only to study the relationship of sediment accumulation conditions detected during drilling with the area, but also to explain the formation conditions of facies based on the well data.

Research methodology

These forms that we have mentioned have been analyzed by many scientists. As a result of the analysis, a special template was developed, which revealed the variation and shapes of the anomaly values of those curves. The most used are the forms of the curves developed according to D.A. Bush and O. Holt, which have funnel-shaped, cylindrical and bell-shaped shapes. Also, these curves are divided into 2 groups, smooth and toothed. The shapes of these curves also

provide information about the conditions of sediment formation.

These received curves were analyzed by V.M. Seyidov and a general form was prepared, whose forms are given in figure 1. Here, there is a SP (GR)-curve with a funnel-shaped shape No. 1 and No. 2, characterized by the regression process that took place in the sea. Curves 3 and 4 have a cylindrical shape, indicating that the process of accumulation of sediments occurs with high intensity and stability. During such a process, a large amount of sand flows into the basin. Forms 5 and 6 of the curve noted in the logging curves are called bell-shaped curves and are associated with the process of sea advance.

Figure 1. Classification of SP (GR) curves against sediments.
1,2-hybrid; 3,4-cylindrical; 5,6-bell; 7-line; 8-fall; 9-bumpy

Also, the fact that the SP (GR) curves are jagged (2,4,6) or smooth (1,3,5) means that the sediment accumulation process is stable or unstable in the part in front of the curve.

Curves number 7, 8, 9 are called linear, concave and convex shapes, respectively. The linear form means that there are no transgression or regression events in the sea, and that the process of sediment accumulation is taking place outside the coast. Sedimentary and depressed shape indicate the parts where the amount of clay material increases (SP and GR curves are characterized by the maximum value in front of the clay layers).

Figure 2. a, b shows an example of structural deltas caused by the influence of channel processes in the distribution of sandy and clayey sediments. In these

deltas, the influence of channel processes prevails. The formation of deltas is related to the activity of river systems as well as the swell and surge of the sea.

When deltas are formed, differences between them arise due to the dominance of wave processes in the distribution of terrigenous material. As a result, the sand cover of the deltas becomes wider. Deltas are characterized by block and bell curves in SP and GR diagrams. Bars and cover deltas are funnel-shaped in SP and GR curves. Sediment between delta channels is represented by sandstones, siltstones and argillites.

Disruptive, sickle-shaped deltas (Fig. 2. c, d) distribution of terrigenous material is related to the activity of swelling and retreating of the sea. They are characterized by a funnel-shaped shape in SP and GR curves.

Figure 2. Facies interpretation of SP curves for delta sediments

1-dry part of the delta plain; 2-sandy sediments of the river bed; 3-remaining channel clay deposits; 4-sand deposits of delta channels; 5-siltstone sediments; 6-shore sediments; coverage of 7-delta channels; 8 the coastline of the sea; 9-shelf silts; 10-genetic interpretation of SP curves-(1-delta channel; 2-sediments between channels; 3-river mouth of delta channels; 4-delta front sediments; 5-delta channel surroundings; 6-sandy part of swell flows; 7-residue delta channel)

Based on mine geophysical data, the facies characteristics of delta channel deposits and sediments separating them are similar to structural deltas.

As for the parameters of the continental group, the facies elements of the listed depositional-hydrodynamic models of the coastal and delta plains separately

have a certain spatial position and an individual shape of the SP (GR) curve. The results of the facies analysis of the wells allow to completely reconstruct the sedimentation model and study the formation conditions, which allows for more efficient exploration of oil and gas reservoirs. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Determination of facies based on the shape of complex logging curves

Calculation results

As we mentioned, the change of various rock petrophysical quantities (porosity, permeability, clay content, oil saturation) along the depth depends directly on the conditions of sediment accumulation.

In the table, the results of the change of a number of petrophysical quantities according to the results of SP curves in the conditional X well of the Pirallahi field

are given. Also, their lithology and oil-saturation characteristics were determined by applying borehole methods

According to the results of the interval SP curves, which is the object of the study, 12 intervals were separated and their lithological composition was considered. As a result of the study, it was determined that the section consists of about 53% clayey sandstone, 46% clay, and 1% pure sandstone. Their oil and gas saturation was also determined.

Layer groups	Selected interval, m	SP	Kpor	Kclay	Ko.sat	Saturation characteristic	Litology
QD (1047.0-1378.0)	1280.4-1289.3	4,61	0,185	0,363	0,57	Oil-gas	silty clayey sandstone
	1297.5-1300.9	4,32	0,214	0,354	0,535	Alternation of clays and oil-gas sandstones	silty clayey sandstone
	1335.6-1337.1	4,45	0,223	0,356	0,53	Oil-gas	sandstone silt clay
	1372.2-1375.9	4,06	0,221	0,314	0,576	Oil-gas	sandstone silt clay
QA (1378.0-1675.0)	1379-1383.9	4,23	0,209	0,319	0,504	Oil-gas	sandstone silt clay
	1436.3-1439.4	3,74	0,227	0,25	0,534	Oil-gas	sandstone silt clay
	1463.9-1468.3	2,79	0,217	0,148	0,776	Oil-gas	sandstone with siltstone
	1489.0-1491.0	3,35	0,203	0,205	0,648	Weak residual oil-gas	sandstone with siltstone
	1502.2-1515.0	2,51	0,216	0,118	0,773	Oil-gas	sandstone with siltstone
	1545.6-1554.3	2,52	0,229	0,081	0,858	Oil-gas	sandstone
	1280.4-1289.3	2,72	0,194	0,113	0,655	Weak residual oil-gas	sandstone with siltstone
	1297.5-1300.9	2,14	0,211	0,077	0,853	Oil-gas	sandstone

Conclusions

Given the variety of facies conditions, the interpretation is carried out in a certain sequence. Sediment accumulation conditions are determined based on the shapes of various logging curves.

The facies analysis method conducted in deep drilling wells is one of the most common and accurate types of research. This method is based on the study of SP or GR core data. Comparisons made with borehole methods allow not only to study the relationship of sediment accumulation conditions detected during drilling with the area, but also to explain the formation conditions of facies based on well data.

Thus, improper assessment of facies indicators and lack of a sedimentation model in the formation of productive layers leads to the drilling of unfounded wells and the violation of the operational sequence of layers in the fields. The application of modern logging methods creates opportunities for the search for hydrocarbon resources in the field and the successful implementation of exploration works.

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